

MEDICINAL PLANTS GROWN IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR MEDICINAL PROPERTIES.

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Abstract: by the 21st century, along with the use of artificially prepared drugs in the treatment of almost all diseases, the demand for medicinal plants is also increasing. This article talks about medicinal plants and their properties.

Key words: medicinal plants, living nature, vitamin, ether, oil.

Medicinal plants are plants used for the treatment of humans and animals, for the prevention of diseases, as well as in the food, perfumery and cosmetic industries. It has been determined that there are 10-12 thousand species of medicinal plants on earth. The chemical and pharmacological properties of more than 1000 plant species have been investigated. There are more than 700 species of medicinal plants in Uzbekistan. Of these, about 120 species of plants grown in natural conditions and cultivated are used in scientific and folk medicine. Currently, about 40-47% of medicines used in medicine are obtained from raw plant materials. Plants are living natural chemical laboratories with complex structures and the ability to create complex organic substances or compounds from simple inorganic substances. Dried herbs, shoots, roots, rhizomes, buds, bulbs, barks, leaves, flowers, buds, fruits (seeds), seeds, juice, pulp, essential oil, etc. are used medicinally.

Medicinal plants are classified in 2 different ways: 1) based on the composition of active substances - alkaloids, glycosides, essential oils, vitamins, etc., 2) based on their pharmacological properties - sedative, analgesic, hypnotic, affecting the cardiovascular system, central nervous system stimulant, blood pressure reducer, etc. The active substances of medicinal plants can be alkaloids, various glycosides, flavonoids, coumarins, astringent and mucilaginous substances, essential oils, vitamins, dyes, enzymes, phytoncides, starch, proteins, polysaccharides, nitrogenous substances, oil and fatty acids and other compounds.

The effect of medicinal plants on the body depends on the amount of chemical compounds in its composition. These compounds accumulate in various parts of the plant. The period of high effectiveness and quality of the drug corresponds to the time of the beginning of their flowering and seeding

period. Medicinal substances are stored in the bud, leaf or stem of some plants, in the flower or fruit of some plants, in the root or bark of some plants. Therefore, the part of plants with the most biologically active substances is harvested. Roots, rhizomes, bulbs and buds of plants are usually prepared during the period when the plant goes into sleep - in late autumn or before the plant wakes up - in early spring. The fruits and seeds of the plant are collected when they are ripe, because they are rich in medicinal substances at this time. Freshly harvested medicinal plant product contains moisture (up to 85% in the above-ground organs, up to 45% in the roots). If this moisture is not removed (by drying), the plant will rot and the medicinal substances will break down and become unusable.

People have been using medicinal herbs to treat diseases since ancient times. 3-4 thousand years ago, India, China, Qad. In the countries of Egypt, works containing information about medicinal plants were written. In the East, in particular, in the folk medicine of Central Asia, treatment using medicinal plants has its own history. has traditions. Regarding the use of medicinal plants for medical purposes, Abu Ali Ibn Sina's work "Al-Qanun" contains information about the medicinal properties of about 476 plants and the methods of their use. Now. During this period, the types of medicinal plants increased, and folk medicine was enriched with medicinal plants. More than medicinal plants, pomegranate, bitter gourd, almond, gorse, medicinal gulhary, walnut, jag-jag, zubturum, frankincense, dogwood, amonkara, pistachio tree, sachartki, chayot, shildirbosh, shirminiya, wormwood, yantoq, mint, kiikot, tograyhon, rubella, rubella, and others are widespread. Paxicarpine from bitter gourd, psoralen from gorse, garmin from frankincense, anabazin from gorse, galantamine from gorse, spherophysin from sedum, etc. alkaloids are obtained. An anthelmintic pelterin tanate and an extract are prepared from pomegranate seeds. Medicinal gulkhairi preparations are expectorants and softeners, medicines made from jag-jagi and lagochilus stop bleeding, and medicines made from pistachio and tea tree are used in the treatment of stomach diseases. S.Q. Islambekov At the Tashkent pharmaceutical plant named after, various medicines are prepared from medicinal plants grown and cultivated in Uzbekistan. The Institute of Chemistry of Plant Substances of Uzbekistan FA has a great service in finding medicinal plants and extracting alkaloids from them. Various organs of more than 4,000 plants were studied in Int for the purpose of obtaining alkaloids, and about 1,000 natural compounds were isolated from them. On this basis, more than 20 valuable drugs such as cytisine and galantamine were created and

introduced into medicine. Essential oil, medicinal and dye plants of the Institute of Botany and Botanical Garden of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. scientific staff in cooperation with specialists created the "Bile-inducing Hojimatov compound" prepared from the raw materials of medicinal plants that are ecologically clean and highly effective in the treatment of jaundice (hepatitis), the most dangerous of the common infectious diseases in the region of Central Asia, and this compound is allowed to be used and produced in scientific medicine done. Also, the technology of planting medicinal plants is studied at the Department of Botany of SamSU, Tashkent State Institute of Pharmaceuticals. There are special farms that grow medicinal plants in Tashkent, Namangan, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya regions and Khorezm Mamun Academy. The raw materials of wild medicinal plants are mainly produced by the republican state-joint-stock concern "Uzfarmsanoat", matlubot companies and the farms of the "Shifobakhsh" production association of the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Management of Uzbekistan.

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